

Final report to WANZ

Bioeconomy Science Institute Wikimedian in Residence
September 2025 - June 2026

by

[Siobhan Leachman](#)

Wikimedian in Residence
Bioeconomy Science Institute
[0000-0002-5398-7721](tel:0000-0002-5398-7721)

[Leanne Elder](#)

Bioeconomy Science Institute
[0000-0001-5244-9780](tel:0000-0001-5244-9780)

[Participants of the Wikidata workshop held at the BSI Auckland site.](#) Siobhan Leachman [CC0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.21142427](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21142427)

Reuse Licence: [CC BY 4.0](#)

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Wikidata.....	3
Documentation.....	4
Wikimedia Commons.....	4
Documentation.....	4
Wikipedia.....	4
WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model.....	5
Engagement with and training of BSI staff.....	5
BSI Engagement Strategy.....	5
Other.....	5
Communications with wider Wiki communities.....	5
Further outreach about WiR work.....	5
Funding.....	5
Introduction	6
Background	6
WiR goals	7
WiR preparation work	8
Zenodo.....	9
Editing work undertaken during the WiR	10
Wikidata.....	10
Biota of New Zealand IDs.....	10
New Zealand Arthropod Collection Collectors/Determiners.....	12
“Collection items at” statements.....	13
Fungal Foray Wikidata items.....	14
“Wikifying” a publication.....	15
Linking collections to scholarly publications.....	16
Upload of BSI related publication citation metadata to Wikidata.....	17
Creation of Wikidata items for NZAC holotype specimens.....	17
OpenRefine project to add Des Helmore illustrations to Wikidata items.....	18
WiR documentation Wikidata items.....	19
Wikimedia Commons.....	19
Category:Landcare Research.....	19
Commons Impact Metrics tool.....	20
Category:Images from the DSIR.....	21
Documentation to support Wikimedia Commons uploads by employees.....	21
Bulk uploads of specimen images via OpenRefine.....	22
Upload of Allan Herbarium handwriting samples.....	22

Des Helmore illustrations.....	23
Wikipedia.....	23
WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model.....	24
Documentation.....	25
Outreach about WikiProject.....	26
Engagement with and training of BSI staff.....	26
ASBS Conference workshops.....	26
Site visits.....	27
Meetings.....	27
WikiCon Wellington.....	28
Workshops.....	28
Updating Wiki communities and others on the WiR.....	31
BSI Engagement Strategy.....	32
Other outcomes.....	32
Future initiatives and outreach.....	33
BSI contributions and organisational outcomes.....	33
BSI in kind contribution.....	33
BSI organisational outcomes.....	34
Conclusion.....	36

Executive summary

This report summarises the work produced by the Wikimedian in Residence (WiR) of the Bioeconomy Science Institute (BSI). This residency, undertaken by Wikimedian Siobhan Leachman (User:Ambrosia10) and overseen by Leanne Elder (User:User:ZoologicalLee) from the BSI, was a part time position running from the 8th of September 2025 until the 30th of June 2026 and achieved the following:

Wikidata

- Enriched existing or created new New Zealand taxon Wikidata items and linking the same to Biota of New Zealand database identifiers
- Created and enriched collector/determiner Wikidata items related to the New Zealand Arthropod Collection (NZAC)
- Added “collection items at” statements to relevant collector Wikidata items for the NZAC, the New Zealand Fungorium and the Allan Herbarium
- Created and enriched Wikidata items for the overarching event the New Zealand Fungal Foray and for each iteration of this annual event
- Wikified the publication *Guide to the sawflies and woodwasps (Hymenoptera, Symphyta) of New Zealand* (<https://doi.org/10.7931/J2/FNZ.81>) and created a workflow to train BSI staff in editing Wikidata, Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons.
- Created or enriched Wikidata items for a dataset of scholarly articles and linked them to the NZAC GBIF dataset thus creating a workflow to illustrate the impact of BSI collections on science
- Created or enriched Wikidata items for BSI related publications sourced from a BSI library dataset and provided by BSI library staff
- Created or enriched Wikidata items for over 3000 NZAC holotype specimens
- Added over 700 Des Helmore scientific illustrations to appropriate Wikidata taxon items

Documentation

Produced the following documentation to support the Wikidata editing of BSI staff:

[Creating a new Wikidata taxon item](#)

["Wikifying" a scholarly publication](#)

[Linking publications to collections](#)

[Biota of New Zealand IDs to Wikidata Workflow](#)

[Bionomia/OpenRefine/Wikidata "Collection items at" workflow](#)

[Wikidata data model for Natural History type specimens](#)

[Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikidata](#)

[New Zealand Arthropod Collection holotype specimen Wikidata upload dataset](#)

[Creation of type specimen Wikidata items via OpenRefine](#)

Wikimedia Commons

- Reorganised Category:Landcare Research creating subcategories and adding an impact metrics tool to assist BSI to gauge impact
- Added categories to the Category:Images from the DSIR and enriched the structured data. Also added a WiR banner confirming the permission for, and the open Creative Commons copyright licensing of, the uploaded images
- Bulk uploaded a set of Allan Herbarium handwriting samples, with categories and appropriate structured data.
- Added comprehensive structured data statements to each of the files in Category:Illustrations of Des Helmore

Documentation

Produced the following documentation to support the upload of images to and the editing of Wikimedia Commons by BSI staff:

[Wikimedia Commons uploads : Uploading of Images by an employee of the copyright holder](#)

[Uploading specimen images via OpenRefine into Wikimedia Commons](#)

[Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images](#)

[Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikimedia Commons + SDC](#)

Wikipedia

- Editing of various Wikipedia articles either to provide examples for documentation or to illustrate to staff the potential for sharing expert knowledge on that platform

WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model

- Collaborated with Auckland War Memorial Museum to produce a Wikidata item data model for type specimens and a Wikimedia Commons structured data model for specimen images. This collaboration is ongoing and now includes staff from the National Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa

Engagement with and training of BSI staff

- Trained BSI staff via the pre, post and in person workshops offered during the WikiProject ASBS Conference 2025
- Undertook two site visits
- Undertook two in person full day workshops at BSI sites
- Undertook in person training of Leanne Elder
- Participated in multiple virtual meetings with staff

BSI Engagement Strategy

- Created a [BSI engagement strategy with Wikimedia platforms](#)

Other

Communications with wider Wiki communities

- GLAMwiki newsletters
- Updates via Wellington and Aotearoa New Zealand Wiki meetups
- Wiki telegram groups for Wikidata, Aotearoa New Zealand, WikiProject Biodiversity and the BHL-Wiki working group
- Presentation at Wikicon Wellington showcasing the approach and aims of this WiR
- Presentation on type specimen data model to Wikidata WikiProject Days 2026

Further outreach about WiR work

- An abstract on the type specimen data model created during the WiR has been submitted to the [Biodiversity Information Standards TDWG 2026 conference](#).

Funding

This project was funded by both Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand and BSI. It received SSIF Infrastructure funding for the Nationally Significant Collections Databases to Landcare Research, New Zealand (internal project numbers PRJ5161).

Introduction

This report summarises the work undertaken by the Wikimedian in Residence (WiR) of the Bioeconomy Science Institute (BSI). This residency, undertaken by Wikimedian Siobhan Leachman (User:Ambrosia10) and overseen by Leanne Elder (User:ZoologicalLee) from the BSI, was a part time position running from the 8th of September 2025 until the 30th of June 2026 and was funded by Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand (WANZ) and BSI.

This report will outline the contributions made during the residency to Wikidata, Wikimedia Commons and Wikipedia, the meetings and training undertaken with BSI staff, the documentation generated including the BSI Wikimedia strategy document, the outreach and engagement undertaken with the wider Wiki community, and other outcomes resulting from WiR work. It will also cover continuing projects resulting from the WiR and likely future outreach opportunities arising as a result of the work undertaken during the residency.

Background

Leanne Elder, the Senior Technician in Imaging and Digitisation - at the time of the original funding application with Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (MWLR) and now with the BSI - made a funding application to WANZ for the purposes of hiring a WiR for her organisation.

Elder was first introduced to the impact engagement with Wikimedia platforms through a keynote presentation undertaken at the iDigBio ADBC Summit in Gainesville, Florida by Siobhan Leachman in early October 2019.¹ Subsequently Elder relocated to New Zealand to work for MWLR. Recognising the potential of Wikimedia engagement to extend the reach, reuse and impact of her institution's digital images and data, she successfully applied for a grant to fund a Wikimedian in Residence at MWLR.

Wikimedian Siobhan Leachman was chosen for the position. The WiR was to be a part time position originally anticipated to last a year at 20 hours per week or for a total of 900 hours of work. However, on the 1st of July 2025, not long after the successful funding application, MWLR was merged along with other government research institutes into the newly formed BSI.

¹ ADBC Summit 2019 report. *iDigBio*. Retrieved May 26, 2026. <https://web.archive.org/web/20260217051741/https://www.idigbio.org/content/adbc-summit-2019-report>

This merger delayed the commencement of the WiR until the week beginning the 8th of September 2025. This delay resulted in the WiR working more hours per week than originally planned to fulfil the total contracted hours requirement of the contract. However, the merger of WMLR into BSI also resulted in the WiR encompassing a greater than anticipated range of people, collections and institutions than originally envisioned.

WiR goals

A major goal of the WiR was to assist the employees of the MWLR group in particular, and BSI in general, to embed their collections, research, and expertise into Wikimedia platforms (Wikipedia, Wikidata, Wikimedia Commons).

The WiR was asked to engage with and educate BSI staff on Wikimedia platforms including educating staff on the impact of sharing BSI content on those platforms and how data reuse can be facilitated by those platforms.

The WiR was tasked with identifying ways to integrate staff engagement with Wikimedia platforms into their work and to develop long term workflows to support staff in undertaking that engagement.

Finally the WiR was requested to produce a Wikimedia engagement strategy to assist BSI staff in sharing their expert knowledge as well as data and content sourced from BSI's nationally significant scientific collections, databases, and publications, increasing the discoverability, accessibility and reusability of those publicly owned resources.

WiR preparation work

Screenshot of NZBSI WiR page. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

At the beginning of the WiR, a Wikipedia page was created (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:GLAM/NZBSI>), as was a Wikidata item (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136395985>) and a Wikimedia Commons category (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:New_Zealand_Bioeconomy_Science_Institute_Wikimedian_in_Residence). This page, item and category were used to collate and to track work undertaken during the WiR. The Wikipedia page also supplied an avenue for engagement with the wider Wiki community and served as a central repository for event information, publications, resources and reports.

At the beginning of the WiR an audit of the current content of the MWLR group of BSI within Wikimedia platforms was undertaken. This overview assisted with the planning of the work to be undertaken during the WiR. Work priorities for the WiR were also set through discussions and meetings, both virtually and in person, with Leanne Elder and the MWLR group collection managers.

Zenodo

The screenshot displays the Zenodo community interface for the 'New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute Wikimedian in Residence 2025-2026' project. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation options like 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. The main content area shows 16 results found, sorted by 'Newest'. Two records are visible:

- NZBSI Lincoln Wiki Workshop Slides and Script**: Uploaded on May 20, 2026. It is a presentation with 68 views and 123 downloads. The description mentions it was for a workshop held at the Lincoln site on May 20, 2026.
- NZBSI Auckland Workshop script**: Uploaded on May 15, 2026. It is also a presentation.

A 'Publication date' bar chart shows two bars representing these uploads. The interface also includes a 'New upload' button and navigation tabs for 'Records', 'Requests', 'Members', and 'Settings'.

Screenshot of the Zenodo Community for the New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute Wikimedian in Residence 2025-2026. CERN. [CC0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Much of the work intended to be undertaken during this WiR was applicable to other natural history institutions. At the beginning of the WiR, Siobhan thought strategically about how to raise awareness of the documentation created and presentations given during the WiR. In particular she was keen to ensure the training documentation and proposed data models created during the residency reached as wide an audience as possible. The intention was to increase the impact of this WiR.

Therefore as part of the initial preparation work for the WiR, Siobhan created a community on the general purpose open-access research and data repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/nzbsiwir/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=20>). This provided a focused public repository for workflow documentation, presentation slide decks and scripts, as well as datasets created during the WiR. Uploading content to this repository was in addition to uploading documents into Wikimedia Commons.

Placing the WiR generated resources into Zenodo provided an alternative avenue of access for the biodiversity and research communities. Zenodo also generated a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for each publication which improved the access and linking to, as well as the reuse of, these publications. Unlike Wikimedia Commons, Zenodo tracks engagement with documentation placed on that platform providing summaries of the number of views as well as download metrics for each upload. These metrics helped gauge the impact of documentation generated during the WiR.

The WiR undertook significant work to ensure the Biota of New Zealand database identifiers were added to appropriate New Zealand taxon Wikidata items. The Biota of New Zealand database was prioritised as it is constantly being updated by BSI staff. Updates to this database also include taxonomic changes to New Zealand native and endemic species.

The workflow used by the WiR to add the Biota of New Zealand identifier to appropriate Wikidata items also ensured these taxonomic changes were reflected in Wikidata. This was important as this assists Wikimedia platforms in being taxonomically up to date.

Documentation was produced to support BSI staff and other Wiki editors wishing to undertake this workflow. This documentation was uploaded into Wikimedia Commons

(https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:A_workflow_for_adding_Biota_of_NZ_ids_to_Wikidata_taxon_items.pdf) and Zenodo

(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18295158>). As of the 25th of June this workflow has been viewed 67 times and downloaded 40 times in Zenodo.

File:Creating a new Wikidata taxon item.pdf

File Discussion Read Edit View history Page Tools TW

Download Use this file Use this file Email a link Information

Creating a new Wikidata taxon item

Siohhan Leechman
Wikimediam in Residence
Biology Science Institute
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5398-7721>
November 2025
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17704502](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17704502)

[Search for taxon item](#)
[Manually creating a taxon item](#)
[List of taxon items](#)
[Taxon rank](#)
[Search \(beta\)](#)
[Data model for a taxon Wikidata item](#)
[Other statements](#)

Search for taxon item

When creating a new Wikidata taxon item, FIRST search Wikidata for that taxon. Creating duplicate items is discouraged and searching for the taxon item will reduce the risk of this occurring.

Items Search

Search for pages containing Panaxosia nigra

Search results

To search for Wikidata items by their title on a given site, use [Special:Search/Title](#).

Search

Advanced search: Search

Search in: Search

There were no results matching the query. You may [create a new item](#) for "Panaxosia nigra".

Screenshot of search of Wikidata items for the newly described Mal moth species Panaxosia nigra. Wikimedia Foundation. CC BY-SA 4.0

Go to page 1

next page →

[Screenshot of Creating a new Wikidata taxon item](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17807008](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17807008)

As part of this work the WiR also created documentation to support BSI staff and others to manually create new taxon Wikidata items. This publication was uploaded to Wikimedia Commons

(https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Creating_a_new_Wikidata_taxon_item.pdf) and Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/17807008>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed 233 times and downloaded 98 times in Zenodo.

New Zealand Arthropod Collection Collectors/Determiners

At the request of the New Zealand Arthropod Collection (NZAC), Wikidata items relating to the collectors and determiners of specimens held within that collection were created or enriched.

The screenshot displays the Bionomia profile for the 'New Zealand Arthropod Collection - Symbiota' dataset. The page header shows navigation options like Profiles, Scribes, Organizations, Datasets, Articles, Countries, Families, and Agent Strings. The main content area features a green progress bar indicating that 19% of the 78 people listed have been attributed specimens. Below the progress bar, a grid of cards lists individual collectors and determiners, including their names, dates, and the types of specimens they collected or identified. The list includes:

- Esmond Hurworth Atkinson** (1888 - 1941, New Zealand): Collected Pucciniaceae and identified Stemonitidaceae.
- John Bain** (1946 - 2018, New Zealand): Collected Braconidae and identified Cerambycidae.
- Ross Beever** (January 03, 1946 - June 03, 2010, New Zealand): Collected Asparagaceae and identified Asparagaceae.
- Anthony Erskine Beveridge** (1925 - July 27, 2020, New Zealand): Collected Podocarpaceae and identified Podocarpaceae.
- Thomas Broun** (July 15, 1839 - August 24, 1919, New Zealand): Collected Carabidae and identified Staphylinidae.
- Thomas Buckley** (New Zealand): Collected Staphylinidae and identified Phasmatidae.
- Seth Bybee**: Collected Scarabaeidae.
- Ewen Cameron**: Collected Poaceae and identified Poaceae.
- Chris Carlton**: Collected Staphylinidae and identified Staphylinidae.

[Screenshot of the Bionomia New Zealand Arthropod Collection - Symbiota profile](#) as at 7 October 2025.

Bionomia. Reused with permission.

This work included using the Bionomia website (<https://bionomia.net/>) to assist with attributing specimens to appropriate specimen collectors or determiners. At the start of this process the Bionomia profile for the NZAC - Symbiota dataset was 19% complete. That is 19% of the occurrence records in that dataset were digitally connected to collector or determiner Wikidata item QIDs or ORCID IDs. In order to increase this percentage of attribution, the WiR created or linked Wikidata items for deceased collectors/determiners or discovered existing ORCID identifiers for living collectors/determiners (linking to the same in Wikidata) and then propagating that identifier in Bionomia.

New Zealand Arthropod Collection - Symbiota
<https://gbif.org/dataset/38e0b5be-be0a-4948-ad2e-fb009652c5b3>

The focus is on terrestrial arthropods from the New Zealand region but there are substantial holdings from South Pacific countries and of mites and nematodes from New Zealand. Material comes from the 1880s to the present day. There are over 1.2 million pinned insects, ~100,00 microscope slides, and 250,000 vials of ethanol preserved specimens. Ecdysis is being used as a platform for workflows associated with mass digitisation. Biocultural (BC) Notice. The BC (Biocultural) Notice is a visible notification that there are accompanying cultural rights and responsibilities that need further attention for any future sharing and use of this material or data. The BC Notice recognizes the rights of Indigenous peoples to permission the use of information, collections, data and digital sequence information (DSI) generated from the biodiversity or genetic resources associated with traditional lands, waters, and territories. The BC Notice may indicate that BC Labels are in development and their implementation is being negotiated.

Primary administrative contact
 wardda@landcareresearch.co.nz

Frictionless Data
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10510383
 collectors & determiners: 208 Code

Refresh

208 people claimed or were attributed specimens represented in this dataset
 Progress: 73%

Name	Country	Specimens Collected
Julia Allwood	New Zealand	Collected Curculionidae
Gilbert Archey	August 04, 1890 – October 20, 1974	Collected Geophilidae and identified Geophilidae
John Scaife Armstrong	June 09, 1892 – February 07, 1977 New Zealand	Collected Syrphidae and identified Cordulidae
James S. Ashe	February 23, 1947 – December 27, 2005 United States	Collected Staphylinidae and identified Staphylinidae
Peter D. Ashlock	August 1929 – January 26, 1989 United States	Collected Lygaeidae and identified Lygaeidae
Volker Assing	November 24, 1956 – September 23, 2022 Germany	Identified Staphylinidae
Esmond Hurworth Atkinson	1888 – 1941 New Zealand	Collected Pucciniaceae and identified Stemonitidaceae
John Bain	1946 – 2018 New Zealand	Collected Braconidae and identified Cerambycidae
Olivier Ball		Collected Myrmaridae

[Screenshot of the Bionomia New Zealand Arthropod Collection - Symbiota profile](#) as at 8 June 2026. Bionomia. Reused with permission.

By the 25th of June 2026 the Bionomia profile for the NZAC - Symbiota dataset was 73% complete. This level of completeness is high in comparison to other Bionomia datasets.

This dataset was unable to reach 100% completeness as, where a collector/determiner is living and they have failed to create an ORCID identifier, it is not possible to attribute specimens to that collector/determiner via Bionomia. As a result of this, discussions were held with BSI employees, and in particular with Leanne Elder, on how BSI could encourage living collectors/determiners to obtain an ORCID and then share that identifier with relevant BSI collection managers. A suggestion that ORCIDs be obtained for living collectors and determiners was added to the BSI strategy engagement document.

“Collection items at” statements

The WiR ensured that all the Wikidata items for the specimen collectors or determiners of the NZAC, the New Zealand Fungorium and the Allan Herbarium had “collection items at” statements added to their Wikidata items. This statement links the Wikidata item for those collectors to the Wikidata items for those collections. This work helped improve the visibility of those BSI collections and also improved their interconnectedness within the wider biodiversity knowledge graph.

“Wikifying” a publication

File:“Wikifying” a scholarly publication.pdf

File [Discussion](#) [Read](#) [Edit](#) [View history](#) ★ Page ▾ Tools ▾ TW ▾

[Download](#) [Use this file](#) [Use this file](#) [Email a link](#) [Information](#) [x](#)

“Wikifying” a scholarly publication

Sibben Leachman
Wikimedia in Residence
Bioeconomy Science Institute
ORCID: [0000-0002-5388-7721](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5388-7721)
November 2023
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17635843>

Table of Contents

- [Introduction](#)
 - [Adding a publication and its data to Wikidata](#)
 - [Creating Wikidata item for article](#)
 - [Creating a Wikidata item if the article has a DOI](#)
 - [Bulk creation of scholarly article Wikidata items](#)
 - [Encoding an article Wikidata item](#)
 - [Author statements](#)
 - [Article identifiers](#)
 - [Full work available at URL](#)
 - [Main subject statements](#)
 - [Class work statements](#)
 - [Usage](#)
 - [Scholarship domains](#)
 - [Example](#)
- [Adding data from an article to Wikidata](#)
- [Encoding Author items](#)
- [Encoding taxa items](#)
- [Examples of statements added to taxa Wikidata items](#)
- [Adding images from a publication to Wikimedia Commons](#)
 - [Copyright of images](#)
 - [Openly licensed images](#)
- [Adding information from a publication to Wikipedia](#)
 - [Conflict of interest](#)
 - [Copyright](#)
 - [Copyrighted publication](#)
 - [Openly licensed publication](#)
 - [Use of a publication in Wikipedia articles](#)
 - [Conclusion](#)

Reuse License Statement: © Sibben Leachman. Unless indicated otherwise for specific images, this report is licensed for reuse under the [Creative Commons Attribution CC BY license](#). Please note that this license does not apply to any images. These specific terms may be revealed as indicated in the image rights statement near the image. In essence, you are free to copy, distribute and adapt this report, so long as you abide by the other license terms.

Go to page

[next page →](#)

Screenshot of “Wikifying” a scholarly publication. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17635843](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17635843)

This documentation was created to teach BSI staff how contributing their expertise can enrich multiple Wikimedia platforms with scientific knowledge and expertise. The documentation guides BSI staff, other authors of scholarly publications, as well as Wiki editors in the editing of Wikidata, Wikimedia Commons and Wikipedia and how to appropriately share the knowledge contained in publications on those various Wikimedia platforms. In creating this documentation the WiR “wikified” the publication *Guide to the sawflies and woodwasps (Hymenoptera, Symphyta) of New Zealand* (<https://doi.org/10.7931/J2/FNZ.81>) to illustrate appropriate “wikifying” and ensured the Wikidata item for this publication (Q109513183) (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q109513183>) served as the model scholarly article item for this workflow.

This workflow was uploaded in both Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:%E2%80%9CWikifying%E2%80%9D_a_scholarly_publication.pdf) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17635843>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 85 times and downloaded 76 times.

Linking collections to scholarly publications

File:Linking publications to collections - adding cites work, uses or acknowledged statements to Wikidata.pdf

File Discussion Read Edit View history ★ Page Tools TW

Download Use this file Use this file Email a link Information

Linking publications to collections

Adding cites work, uses or acknowledged statements to Wikidata

Siothán Leachman
Wikimedian in Residence
Biodiversity Science Institute
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5396-7721>
November 2023
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17706250](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17706250)

Motivation
Publications attached to a GBIF dataset
Wikidata item for dataset in GBIF
Data model for a GBIF occurrence dataset Wikidata item
Download the citations attached to the dataset.
User:Eluffa
Bibliography
Unpublished publications
Adding 'cites work' statement
Publications that cite collection specimens
Publications that acknowledge collections, institutions, or staff.
Querying Wikidata
Acknowledgements

Motivation

Natural history collections are vital for documenting biodiversity and for scientific research. These collections also provide data crucial for supporting the bioeconomy as well as scientific fields such as taxonomy and conservation.

To improve recognition of the value of natural history collections, the reuse of these collections and their data in research needs to be well documented. This paper outlines simple workflows for adding 'cites work', 'uses' and 'acknowledges' statements to Wikidata items for publications. These statements link publications to natural history collections where the data or specimens of that collection has assisted with the generation of those publications. This linking can help enhance the visibility of natural history collections and highlight their impact on science. Such linking can help reflect the value of natural history collections and their data to science.

Reuse License Statement: © Siothán Leachman. Unless indicated otherwise for specific images, this report is licensed for reuse under the [Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/). Please note that this license does not apply to any images. Those specific terms may be revised as indicated in the image rights statement near the image. In essence, you are free to copy, distribute and adapt this report, so long as you abide by the other license terms.

Go to page 1

Publications attached to a GBIF dataset

next page →

Screenshot of [Linking publications to collections workflow documentation](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17706250](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17706250)

Repeated requests by BSI staff affiliated with the NZAC, the New Zealand Fungorium and the Allan Herbarium were made to the WiR for any Wiki work that may help to illustrate the impact of BSI collections.

These discussions inspired the creation of a Wiki workflow aimed at linking publications that use BSI collections to the collections themselves. Several Wikidata items for relevant scholarly articles were edited to illustrate this workflow. These edits assisted the production of workflow documentation which was published in both Wikimedia Commons

(https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Linking_publications_to_collections_-_adding_cites_work,_uses_or_acknowledged_statements_to_Wikidata.pdf) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17706250>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 678 times and downloaded 175 times.

A Wikidata SPAQL query was also created to list scholarly articles that cite the NZAC-Symbiota GBIF occurrence dataset (<https://w.wiki/FkJE>).

Upload of BSI related publication citation metadata to Wikidata

The above work, as well as a meeting with the BSI library staff, resulted in the WiR obtaining a raw dataset of citation data relating to publications by staff affiliated with the BSI. This dataset included both scholarly articles with DOIs as well as publications published by the BSI or its predecessors.

The WiR placed this raw dataset in OpenRefine, cleaned the data and then reconciled it against Wikidata. Pleasingly over half the publications already had Wikidata items. A batch upload was then undertaken for those publications that did not yet have a Wikidata item. This led to the creation of just over 4000 additional Wikidata items. Work on disambiguating the authors of those articles continues.

Creation of Wikidata items for NZAC holotype specimens

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for a dataset titled "Wikidata WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model". The record is published on March 5, 2026, and is version 1. The dataset is titled "New Zealand Arthropod Collection holotype specimen Wikidata upload" and is authored by Siobhan Leachman. The description states that the dataset is an xlsx spreadsheet generated from an OpenRefine project, used to create Wikidata items for holotype specimens from the New Zealand Arthropod Collection. The record has 128 views and 15 downloads.

[Screenshot of Zenodo showing documentation titled New Zealand Arthropod Collection holotype specimen Wikidata upload](#). CERN. [CC0](#)

As part of the collaboration Wikidata WikiProject Type Specimen Data model outlined below the WiR batch created Wikidata items for all the holotypes of the NZAC via OpenRefine. A xlsx spreadsheet generated from the OpenRefine project for this work was uploaded into Zendo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18882424>). As this document is an xlsx spreadsheet, it was not able to be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons. As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 142 times and downloaded 16 times.

[Screenshot of workflow for Creation of type specimen Wikidata items via OpenRefine](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18883286](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18883286)

This upload informed not only the type specimen Wikidata item data model but also resulted in the creation of documentation to guide BSI staff and others associated with other natural history collections to replicate the same workflow.

This documentation was published in both Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Creation_of_type_specimen_Wikidata_items_via_OpenRefine.pdf) and in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18883286>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 72 times and downloaded 50 times.

OpenRefine project to add Des Helmore illustrations to Wikidata items
As part of the initial audit of the Wikimedia Commons Category:Landcare Research the WiR realised there was potential to increase the impact of this prior upload of images as the Wikidata property “scientific illustration” (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P13162>) had been created subsequent to that upload. The WiR therefore created an OpenRefine project and ensured all appropriate Des Helmore illustrations were added as a scientific illustration to taxon Wikidata items. This work helps increase both the findability and reuse of these illustrations. It resulted in approximately 760 illustrations being added to Wikidata taxon items.

WiR documentation Wikidata items

The WiR created Wikidata items for each of the documents and workflows created during the WiR. This assisted with linking the citation data, the Zenodo generated DOI and the file placed in Wikimedia Commons for each publication.

Wikimedia Commons

One major focus of this WiR was to support key staff to learn how to appropriately upload BSI collection images into Wikimedia Commons and to integrate this into existing staff workflows.

Category:Landcare Research

Category:Landcare Research ? Help

[Category](#) [Discussion](#) [Read](#) [Edit](#) [View history](#) ☆ [Data for files](#) Page ▾ Tools ▾ TW ▾

Page views for this category ([about](#)) [\[Expand\]](#)

This category contains Creative Commons licensed images of Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research New Zealand Ltd. Landcare Research is one of New Zealand's Crown Research Institutes. Its images focus on the New Zealand environment and biodiversity.

Images in this category should have the [Institution:Landcare Research](#) template in them, and be uploaded from the institutional collection.

[Image Uptake Stats](#)

Subcategories

This category has the following 16 subcategories, out of 16 total.

<p>A</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Allan Herbarium (1 C, 10 F) <p>C</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Carabidae in Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (142 F) ▶ Carvings by Denis Conway (12 F) ▶ Cicadidae in Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (110 F) ▶ Cicindelidae in Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (7 F) ▶ Curculionoidea in Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (491 F) 	<p>F</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Flora of New Zealand Online (13 F) <p>H</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Illustrations by A. C. Harris (1 P, 18 F) ▶ Illustrations by Des Helmore (1077 F) <p>L</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Lepidoptera in Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (1460 F) <p>N</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ New Zealand Arthropod Collection (1 C, 57 F) ▶ New Zealand Fungarium (2 F)
---	--

Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research [\[Collapse\]](#)

New Zealand research institute (1992–2025)

[Upload media](#)

[Wikipedia](#)

Instance of [research institute](#)

Crown Research Institute

Location New Zealand

Chief executive officer James Stevenson-Wallace (2022–)

Headquarters location [Lincoln](#)

Inception 1 July 1992

Dissolved, abolished or demolished date 30 June 2025

Replaced by New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science (2025)

[official website](#)

[Screenshot of Wikimedia Commons Category:Landcare Research](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

At the start of the WiR the Wikimedia Commons Category:Landcare Research (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:Landcare_Research) was reorganised to remove duplication, improve categorisation and allow for the addition of an impact metrics tool to assist BSI to gauge impact. New subcategories were created for collections of images to allow for ease of future uploads as well as the improved organisation of images. Although the renaming or merging of the overarching Category:Landcare Research was considered, the decision was to delay until such time as the ongoing BSI merger was complete.

Commons Impact Metrics tool

[Screenshot of Wikimedia Commons Commons Impact Metrics Page Views of this Category for Category:Landcare Research](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

An important addition to Category:Landcare Research was made during the WiR. The WiR added markup to ensure a Commons Impact Metrics (https://wikitech.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons_Impact_Metrics) summary and its associated visualisations were displayed on the category.

As can be seen from the statistics given by this tool, from the beginning of February 2026 to the end of April 2026 files sourced from the MWLR group of BSI and placed on English Wikipedia pages have been viewed **979,944** times.

Another method for obtaining the above metrics is via querying the Wikimedia Commons API see <https://doc.wikimedia.org/generated-data-platform/aqs/analytics-api/reference/commons.html> using the end point "commons-analytics/pageviews-per-category-monthly", the category "Landcare_Research", the category-scope "deep" and giving a start date and end date.

After this reorganisation of the main Wikimedia Commons category and improving impact metric discoverability, the WiR attempted to gauge the success of previous upload efforts by staff.

Category:Images from the DSIR

This led to the necessary improvement of the batch upload of images placed in [Category:Images from the DSIR](#). The WiR enriched the structured data attached to these images, added categories and also added the WiR banner confirming she had edited the files and had confirmed the permission for, and the open Creative Commons copyright licensing of, the upload on behalf of the MWLR group of the BSI. This ensured this set of files was no longer in danger of being deleted by Wikimedia Commons administrators.

Documentation to support Wikimedia Commons uploads by employees

File:Wikimedia Commons uploads by an employee of the copyright holder.pdf

File Discussion Read Edit View history ★ Page Tools TW

Download Use this file Use this file Email a link Information

Wikimedia Commons uploads
Uploading of images by an employee of the copyright holder

Sibhan Leachman
Wikimedian in Residence
Bioeconomy Science Institute
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7771-1101>
November 2025
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17634556>

Table of contents

- Introduction
- Does the employee have a Wik account?
- Wikimedia Commons user page
- Are the images suitable for Wikimedia Commons?
- Are the images in the public domain?
- Does the organisation own the copyright to the images?
- Under what Creative Commons licence will the files be released?
- Are the images educational?
- Source of the images
- Images published by the employer online
- Images yet to be published by the employer online
- Volunteer Response Team (VRT) process
- Batch upload of images
- Pathplan
- OpenRefine
- Actions after upload
- VRT process
- Reach out to the wider Wiki community
- Impact metrics

Go to page 1

next page →

Re-use License Statement: © Sibhan Leachman. Unless indicated otherwise for specific images, this report is licensed for re-use under the [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC BY\) license](#). Please note that this license does not apply to any images. Those specific terms may be re-used as indicated in the image rights statement near the image. In re-use, you are free to copy, distribute and adapt this report, so long as you abide by the other license terms.

[Screenshot of workflow supporting Wikimedia Commons uploads by an employee of the copyright holder.](#)
Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17634556](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17634556)

The issues raised by the above upload inspired the creation of documentation by the WiR to better support employees to upload images owned by their employer to Wikimedia Commons. This documentation was first placed in Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Wikimedia_Commons_uploads_by_an_employee_of_the_copyright_holder.pdf) and then in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17634556>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 434 times and downloaded 118 times.

Bulk uploads of specimen images via OpenRefine

[Screenshot of documentation supporting the upload of specimen images via OpenRefine into Wikimedia Commons](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18970160](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18970160)

The upskilling of staff focused on one on one tutoring of Leanne Elder in batch uploads of images to Wikimedia Commons via OpenRefine. This required the production of “how to” documentation for this workflow. This documentation was uploaded into Wikimedia Commons

(https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Uploading_specimen_images_via_OpenRefine_into_Wikimedia_Commons.pdf) and Zenodo

(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18970160>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 63 times and downloaded 54 times.

Upload of Allan Herbarium handwriting samples

This Wikimedia Commons upload resulted from a request by the Allan Herbarium to upload handwriting samples of botanists with collections held at that herbarium. These handwriting samples help herbaria identify collectors and determiners of specimens. Prior to this upload the Allan Herbarium had this information on CDs. Unfortunately only the CD for botanists whose surname fell within A to P was available. The CD for family names beginning with Q to Z was unable to be located. The overarching category for this upload is Category:Allan herbarium handwriting samples

(https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:Allan_herbarium_handwriting_samples).

Des Helmore illustrations

The WiR added comprehensive structured data statements to each of the files in Category:Illustrations of Des Helmore (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:Illustrations_by_Des_Helmore) using the Biodiversity Heritage Library illustration data model (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Biodiversity_Heritage_Library/Modeling) as a guide. This improved the interconnectedness of these illustrations to the wider biodiversity knowledge graph and improved the ability of these files being found via SPARQL endpoints such as <https://qlever.dev/wikimedia-commons> and Wikimedia Commons APIs.

Wikipedia

Although direct editing of Wikipedia articles was not a focus of this WiR, some editing of English Wikipedia articles took place. For example the WiR spent time adding BSI sourced images from the Allan Herbarium handwriting upload and also images from Category:Images from the DSIR to appropriate Wikipedia articles. Both of these examples were used to inform workflow documentation or to illustrate to BSI staff the impact of adding images to Wikipedia articles.

Another example of Wikipedia editing undertaken by the WiR was adding citations from a BSI related publication to appropriate Wikipedia articles in order to model the “wikifying” of a scholarly article and again support the creation of this workflow documentation.

WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model

Wikidata:WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model

[Project page](#) [Discussion](#) [Read](#) [Edit](#) [View history](#) ★ Page▼

Welcome	Type Specimen Technical Documentation	Specimen Image Technical Documentation	Crosswalks	Modelling Principles	Specimen Template Review
-------------------------	---	--	----------------------------	---	---

About

This WikiProject supports the development, documentation, and improvement of data models for **natural history specimens** across Wikidata and Structured Data on Commons (SDC). The project aims to create consistent, machine-readable ways to represent specimen records, holotypes, collection events, collectors, taxonomic determinations, and related GLAM-held material.

Currently this data model is being used to guild the creation of holotype specimen Wikidata items only.

Scope

This WikiProject covers:

- Wikidata modelling for natural history specimens (only *notable* specimens, e.g. holotypes as per current wikidata conventions for uploading natural science material)
- Structured Data on Commons (SDC) for specimen images
- Linking specimens to taxonomic names, identifiers, and literature
- Modelling collecting events (collector, date, locality, method)
- Aligning specimen data with external biodiversity standards (GBIF, Darwin Core, BHL)
- Supporting GLAM and Research institutions contributing Natural Sciences material to Commons and Wikidata

Specimen image with structured data statements following the data model.

[Screenshot of Wikidata:WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

A significant piece of work undertaken by the WiR was the collaboration with Brodie Satherley, Online Collections Data Analyst from the Auckland War Memorial Museum, on the Wikidata WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Natural_History_Specimen_Data_Model). This project aims to create consistent, machine-readable ways to represent specimen records, holotypes, collection events, collectors, taxonomic determinations and specimen images in Wikidata and Wikimedia Commons structured data statements.

In collaboration with Satherley, the WiR created the above project page, drafted a proposed Wikidata data model for holotype specimen items, drafted a proposed Wikimedia Commons data model for specimen images, successfully proposed four new Wikidata properties to assist with implementing those data models, created documentation to support the implementation of those data models by natural history institutions and showcased a NZAC holotype specimen OpenRefine project to illustrate bulk creation of Wikidata items following the proposed model.

The data models were also cross-walked to the Biodiversity Information Standards Association Darwin Core data standard (<https://dwc.tdwg.org/>) helping to ensure the interoperability of these two data models.

This work fed into proposed uploads of BSI specimen images and the creation of the NZAC holotype specimen Wikidata items. Preparation for these proposed uploads also resulted in the improvement of NZAC specimen data.

Documentation

Recognising the potential for reuse of these “how to” documents by other Wikimedians and natural history institutions the WiR ensured the supporting documentation for this WikiProject were published on multiple platforms. These documents were included on the Wikidata WikiProject itself, in Wikimedia Commons and in Zenodo.

The following documents were created:

- Wikidata data model for Natural History type specimens - placed in Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Wikidata_data_model_for_Natural_History_type_specimens.pdf) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880276>) As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 68 times and downloaded 48 times.
- Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikidata - placed in Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Crosswalk_for_Natural_History_Specimen_Data_Model_-_Wikidata.png) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18881948>) As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 73 times and downloaded 43 times.
- Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images - placed in Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Wikimedia_Commons_data_model_for_Natural_History_specimen_images.pdf) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400>) As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 80 times and downloaded 38 times.

- Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikimedia Commons + SDC placed in Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Crosswalk_for_Natural_History_Specimen_Data_Model_-_Wikimedia_Commons_%2B_SDC.png) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18881782>) As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 61 times and downloaded 33 times.
- New Zealand Arthropod Collection holotype specimen Wikidata upload spreadsheet. Only available for download via Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18882424>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 142 times and downloaded 16 times.

Outreach about WikiProject

As well as updating the wider Wiki community on the process of this project in the New Zealand section of the GLAMWiki newsletter, a presentation at the Aotearoa New Zealand Wikicon 2026 in Wellington, and a presentation at the Wikidata WikiProject Days 2026 event, the Siobhan has submitted an abstract on this project to the TDWG 2026 conference.

Engagement with and training of BSI staff

A key goal of this WiR was to engage with and educate BSI staff on Wikimedia platforms. This engagement and education took multiple forms during the WiR.

ASBS Conference workshops

Early in the WiR BSI staff were informed of the online and in person Wiki training opportunities being provided to the ASBS Conference (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_ASBS_2025/ASBS_Workshops) by the WiR and her colleague Heidi Meudt. Multiple BSI staff attended the online pre and post Wiki workshops and Jessie Prebble, a botanist with the Allan Herbarium, also attended the ASBS in person workshop.

Site visits

In person visits were arranged for WiR at the Auckland and Lincoln sites in October and November 2025. The WiR had the opportunity to view the collections and to meet with key BSI staff, including collection managers for each collection. During these meetings BSI staff were educated about Wikimedia platforms, the role of a WiR and the work being proposed. The collection managers were also asked what priorities they would like the WiR to concentrate on. Where possible these suggestions were added to the planned work of the WiR.

A meeting was also held with the BSI library staff where the librarians were exposed to the Wiki tool Scholia (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Scholia>). This inspired the library staff to share the BSI related publication citation data and initiated the WiR programme of work relating to those publications as discussed above.

While at the Auckland site the WiR was also able to meet with Brodie Satherley, Online Collections Data Analyst from the Auckland War Memorial Museum, to coordinate efforts toward the work on the Wikidata:WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Natural_History_Specimen_Data_Model).

Meetings

Meetings were regularly held with Leanne Elder to update her on the progress of the residency and to receive insight and feedback on work undertaken. Elder also facilitated access and organising both in person and online meetings with key BSI staff.

Leanne Elder and Nick Kirk both visited Wellington and spent two days in meetings with Siobhan to help organise the two onsite workshops held at the Auckland and Lincoln sites. During one of these days Siobhan had the opportunity to spend one on one time with Elder, training her in uploading images to Wikimedia Commons, adding structured data statements to Wikimedia Commons images and using OpenRefine to bulk upload images to Wikimedia Commons.

Siobhan also attended the monthly BSI collection managers meeting. This was extremely useful in raising awareness of these key BSI staff in the progress of the WiR, the documentation being produced and the training events being offered. It also provided the WiR an opportunity to advocate for open licensing of content in light of the recent merger of MWLR into the BSI.

WikiCon Wellington

Siobhan and Leanne Elder worked together to produce a presentation for the Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand Wiki Con held in Wellington on the 1st to the 3rd of May. This presentation was given by Elder and the slide deck and script were uploaded into Wikimedia Commons

(https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NZBSI_Wikimedian_in_Residence_presentation_at_WikiCon_Aotearoa_New_Zealand_at_Wellington_2026.pdf) as well as Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20318578>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 79 times and downloaded 136 times.

By attending this conference Elder had the opportunity to improve her editing skills, learn more about the Wikiverse, and engage with many of the New Zealand based editors that contribute to Wikimedia platforms.

[Leanne Elder presentation WikiCon Wellington 2026](#) by Stephen A'Court [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) via Wikimedian Commons.

Workshops

The WiR offered two in person workshops aimed at training staff. Prior to the two workshops staff were surveyed to gather information on what information the workshop should provide. This information was used to inform the content of the workshops as well as the topics covered at each site.

[New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute WiR Wikidata workshop in Auckland](#) by Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

The first was held in Auckland on Friday the 15th of May. This full day in person workshop trained **ten** BSI staff and **three** staff from the Auckland War Memorial Museum on Wikidata. The Wiki page for that workshop can be found here https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:GLAM/NZBSI/Auckland_Workshop. The slides and script have been uploaded to Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NZBSI_Auckland_Wikidata_Workshop_15_May_2026_Slides.pdf and https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NZBSI_Auckland_Wikidata_Workshop_15_May_2026_script.pdf) and to Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20318033>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 65 times and downloaded 111 times. This workshop was also recorded and shared on the BSI teams network for viewing by BSI staff unable to attend.

[Attendees at the Lincoln 2026 Wiki Workshop and Siobhan Leachman](#) by Awperyman. [CC0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

The second workshop was held in Lincoln on Wednesday the 20th of May. This full day in person workshop trained **nine** BSI staff in Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons and Wikidata. The Wiki page for this workshop can be found here https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:GLAM/NZBSI/Lincoln_Workshop. The slides and script have been uploaded to Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NZBSI_Lincoln_Wiki_Workshop_Slides.pdf and https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NZBSI_Lincoln_Wiki_Workshop_script.pdf) and to Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20318578>). As of the 25th of June this document has been viewed in Zenodo 79 times and downloaded 136 times. This workshop was also recorded and shared on the BSI teams network for viewing by BSI staff unable to attend.

Updating Wiki communities and others on the WiR

The WiR undertook to keep the local and wider Wikimedia communities updated on the progress of the residency. The Wikipedia page relating to the WiR (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:GLAM/NZBSI>) was kept up to date.

Regular updates on the WiR were given in the New Zealand section of the GLAMWiki newsletter. See <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:GLAM/NZBSI/Reports> for a list of GLAMwiki newsletters containing updates. Regular updates were also given in the in person Wellington Wiki meetup <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Meetup/Wellington> and in the online Aotearoa New Zealand Wiki meetup https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Meetup/Aotearoa_New_Zealand_Online.

The October Global GLAMwiki call was attended to inform participants of GLAMwiki about the project (https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Event:Global_GLAM_call_2025-10-14).

Leanne Elder presented at WikiCon Wellington informing the wider New Zealand editing community about the WiR.

The WiR had a meeting with Shani Evanstein Sigalov, previously a member of the Wikimedia Foundation Board of Trustees and now the lead researcher for the AI-Bridges initiative (<https://ai-bridges.org/>). This discussed the work being undertaken during the WiR and examples of the work being undertaken was provided to the AI Bridges project.

The WiR has presented on the Wikidata:WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model at the Wikidata WikiProject Days 2026 event on Saturday the 20th of June (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Event:WikiProjects_Days_2026#Sessions).

Social media engagement also took place on the LinkedIn, Bluesky, Mastodon, and Facebook platforms publicising the WiR and the work undertaken during the residency.

BSI Engagement Strategy

One of the key goals of this WiR was to produce a Wikimedia platform engagement strategy for the BSI. This has been drafted, has received feedback from BSI staff as well as from Victoria Leachman, prior President of WANZ, and has now been submitted to Leanne Elder, representing the BSI. The strategy has been published in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20725218>), added to Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Bioeconomy_Science_Institute_Engagement_Strategy_with_Wikimedia_Platforms.pdf) and linked to in the Wikipedia page for the WiR (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:GLAM/NZBSI/Engagement_strategy).

Other outcomes

The residency has helped improve the skills of Siobhan in bulk editing, in undertaking training and outreach as well as undertaking a Wikimedian in Residence position. For example this residency has resulted in her extending her skills in using tools such as OpenRefine and in running workshops as an individual organiser.

This residency has resulted in a very fruitful collaboration with the Auckland War Memorial Museum which is now including staff from Te Papa. These collaborations have helped build relationships between key staff at these organisations - BSI, Auckland Museum and Te Papa - as well as with Siobhan.

The WiR has also facilitated access to BSI resources on behalf of other Wiki editors. For example Siobhan helped expedite the Banks Peninsular WikiProject request for specimen images. This request was fulfilled by Leanne Elder.

The WiR served as a conduit for information and presentations obtained via conferences such as Living Data 2026 and the Biodiversity Heritage Library annual meeting. Siobhan assisted Leanne Elder to attend and present at the Aotearoa New Zealand Wellington WikiCon.

Siobhan as WiR was also able to provide feedback to a technical review of the systems that support the Nationally Significant Collections and Databases at BSI. This was important as it ensured the WiR was able to give an end user perspective and feedback about these systems.

Future initiatives and outreach

This WiR has inspired contributions to Wikimedia platforms such as the ongoing work collaborating with staff at the Auckland War Memorial Museum and Te Papa on the Wikidata:WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model. Further work on the data model for both Wikidata type specimen items as well as the structured data on Wikimedia Commons for specimen images will take place. This includes a review and editing of the Wikimedia Commons specimen template.

The WiR has also submitted an abstract to the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) 2026 conference (<https://www.tdwg.org/conferences/2026/>) to present on the Wikidata:WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model.

Finally a proposal for a Wikimedian in Residence meetup at Wikimania 2026 has also recently been accepted and as a result it is likely this WiR will be discussed during Wikimania.

BSI contributions and organisational outcomes

BSI in kind contribution

BSI employee Leanne Elder prepared the grant proposal and budget for the Wikimedian in Residence (WiR) funding. This required significant planning and communication with WANZ staff to understand the application process and ensure the planned work aligned with WANZ priorities.

To support the application, Leanne also documented the case for in-kind funding from MWLR to ensure the project's success. This included identifying staff that would contribute to support the WiR work.

When MWLR transitioned into the new Bioeconomy Science Institute (BSI), the project's institutional value and ongoing support needed to be presented to the new management team. Leanne advocated for the project's importance and strategic benefits, helping secure continued organisational support.

The initial in-kind financial commitment from MWLR (now BSI) was \$40,496 under the "Collections Digitisation Overview" project (internal project number prj5161). This funding covered staff time for Leanne Elder, Nick Kirk and Jessie Prebble to contribute.

In addition to the initial funding, further staff time was provided through other project budgets, including Collections budgets and Staff Development time budgets. This included staff engagement in meetings during the discovery and priority setting meetings with Siobhan and Leanne, as well as for staff attendance and participation in the Wikimedia training workshops.

The original proposal also included a culturomics analysis to be undertaken by a staff member from the economics group. However, that staff member accepted voluntary redundancy during the organisational merger process, so that part of the project was not achieved.

Leanne coordinated the logistics for Siobhan to be familiarised with the BSI way of working including collections, systems and staff. Leanne determined key personnel responsible for data and images that could potentially contribute to Wikimedia platforms and organised introductions during Siobhan's visits to the Lincoln and Auckland sites. These meetings included staff from Knowledge Services (Library), Biological Collections and the Data and Digital team. This overarching coverage resulted in voluntary workshop attendance from across these parts of BSI.

Nick Kirk led the work to ensure compliance with the Social Ethics Committee requirements for the pre and post workshop surveys. Nick, Siobhan and Leanne collaboratively developed the survey questions early in the project to inform workshop planning and content. The post workshop survey provides valuable information to guide future training and engagement activities with NSI staff.

BSI organisational outcomes

Before this project, some BSI staff had been introduced to Wikimedia through Mike Dickison's previous Wikimedian At Large collaboration with MWLR. That work primarily resulted in illustration uploads and presentations highlighting the value of Wikipedia. Mike's work was successful in raising awareness and helping staff understand the types of content that could be shared.

To explore how to move beyond awareness to active participation, Leanne organised meetings with experienced Wikimedia editors including Victoria Leachman, Lucy Schrader and Siobhan Leachman. Through these meetings we concluded that a major barrier was the lack of practical skills needed for staff to plan standardised workflows and contribute effectively. These discussions identified a Wikimedian in Residence as the most effective way to build organisational capability.

The Wikimedian in Residence role enabled Siobhan to gain an understanding of BSI's collections, workflows and technical infrastructure. She then developed extensive practical workflows for staff to effectively contribute data and media to Wikimedia platforms. This work required specialised expertise that did not exist within BSI. Siobhan has extensive Wiki knowledge in how data is connected in Wikimedia platforms and what has impact. Siobhan's unique combination of Wikimedia knowledge and biodiversity expertise enabled her to understand how BSI's collections connect with Wikidata and Wikimedia Commons, identify content with the greatest public value, and design workflows that maximise impact.

Once these workflows were created Siobhan, Nick and Leanne were able to plan workshops to ensure staff could confidently use them. Siobhan then designed training materials and then designed and delivered the two in person training workshops for BSI staff.

As a result, BSI staff now have the capability to contribute to Wikidata and Wikimedia Commons and understand how to access the workflows developed in this project and begin applying them to routine work. From those workshops BSI staff now have capability in Wikidata and Wikicommons to begin contributing, as well as an understanding of how to access Siobhan's workflows. Staff have greater confidence in making decisions about releasing data and images through Wikimedia platforms and possess the practical skills needed to upload and manage that content.

Results from the post workshop survey (as of 2 July) demonstrate these outcomes. Eighty-eight percent of respondents reported that they were more knowledgeable about Wikimedia platforms after participating in the workshops. Seventy-seven percent indicated they were more likely to contribute to Wikimedia platforms than before the training.

The workshops brought together staff from parts of BSI that have common interests, but do currently have projects to collaborate directly on. This momentum will help foster an organisational culture of collaboration around Wikimedia, supporting the continued development and expansion of Wikimedia activities across BSI.

Through the project, Leanne Elder also developed a strong professional network within the Wikimedia community. This network provides ongoing opportunities for advice, collaboration, and knowledge exchange, strengthening BSI's capacity to embed Wikimedia practices into its long-term workflows. As BSI staff capability continues to grow, these relationships will help support future initiatives and ensure access to external expertise.

The connections established through the project have also created opportunities for future collaboration. Discussions are underway about BSI summer student interns participating in the Auckland Museum Wikimedia internship programme, providing additional opportunities to develop Wikimedia skills and contribute to open biodiversity knowledge.

Leanne will build on her skills by participating in the 2026 Species Edit-a-thon, hosted by Heidi Meudt and Siobhan Leachman. Continued involvement in Wikimedia events will further strengthen her knowledge, expand her professional network, and support the ongoing development of Wikimedia capability within BSI.

Conclusion

The goals of this project have all been successfully achieved

- **Developed an organisational strategy for engagement with Wikimedia platforms.** BSI now has a clear strategic approach for contributing biodiversity data and media to Wikimedia platforms and understands the value of ongoing engagement.
- **Established sustainable workflows for long-term contributions.** Practical workflows have been developed to integrate Wikimedia content creation into specimen digitisation and data mobilisation processes, creating opportunities to improve efficiency and support the ongoing publication of biodiversity data and images.
- **Fostered staff capability and engagement.** Staff participated in targeted training and discussions that increased their understanding of:
 - the Wikimedia ecosystem;
 - the value and impact of data reuse through Wikimedia platforms; and
 - the potential of Wikimedia as a tool for increasing the visibility of BSI's biodiversity collections.

In the view of the writers the Bioeconomy Science Institute WiR has been very productive and successful. The WiR helped ensure BSI data and images were shared more widely with Wikidata and Wikicommons. BSI collections and databases have also been improved as a result of inconsistencies being uncovered during the WiR.

BSI staff knowledge and awareness of the Wikiverse was increased as a result of the conversations and meetings with the WiR which took place during site visits, online sessions and during the various workshops and training opportunities offered.

Editing skills of BSI staff were improved as a result of the training opportunities provided during the WiR. Awareness of the potential for Wikidata QID roundtripping in BSI's collection management systems has increased. This roundtripping is likely to be considered once the challenges of merging BSI data management systems have been resolved.

BSI staff now have access to documentation that supports workflows empowering staff to share their expert knowledge, BSI content and data with Wikimedia platforms. Staff are able to use these documents to assist with integrating these efforts into their day to day employment.

BSI has also improved its connections with like-minded institutions such as the Auckland War Memorial Museum and Te Papa as a result of this WiR and connections made between staff at these institutions.

Finally BSI management now has a Wikimedia platform engagement strategy they can use to help guide future engagement and further build on the progress initiated by this WiR.